

Development of Functional Sutures through Electrospinning

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SUMMARY

A novel kind of functional sutures was developed by combining electrospinning with a braiding technique. After post treatments, the electrospun PLLA nanofiber threads which were collected uniaxially were made into a more compact braided wire. Chitosan was used as a coating agent to make the braided wire surface smoothed and functionalized. Morphology and mechanical properties of the PLLA sutures with and without chitosan were studied, blood compatibility and hemostatic behavior were investigated, and biocompatibility was also performed on the chitosan coated sutures. Results showed that nanofibers collected by a high speed rotating disc displayed a preferably uniaxial orientation. There were no differences in tensile performances between the PLLA sutures with and without chitosan coating, but the sutures with chitosan coating showed better blood compatibility and no effect on cellular morphology and proliferation was recognized. The sutures were implanted into SD rats and exhibited favorable tissue compatibility.

Key words: Poly(L-lactic acid); electrospinning; sutures; mechanical property; hemostatic; biocompatibility

INTRODUCTION

Sutures are natural or synthetic textile materials in monofilament, multifilament, twisted, and braided form, which are widely used in wound closure, to ligate injured blood vessels and to draw divided tissues together[1]. Owing to their outstanding properties such as large specific surface area and high porosity with very small pore size, ultrathin or nanofibers by electrospinning have been considered for applications particularly in biomedical fields including tissue engineering scaffolds[11,12], drug release systems[13,14], wound dressing[15] and enzyme immobilization[16]. This work considered an application of electrospun nanofibers for the development of structural biomaterial, i.e., tissue sutures.

Poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA) approved by FDA was applied in this work, because of its biodegradability, biocompatibility and good mechanical properties. However, PLLA does not possess necessary hemostatic and antimicrobial activities. It would be useful to combine the beneficial properties of a natural polymer with the favorable physico-mechanical properties of PLLA. Chitosan is capable of accelerating a wound healing process[21]. When chitosan is coated on the surface of a PLLA suture, it can interact directly with cells whereas PLLA provides both mechanical strength and stiffness to a biodegradable device.

EXPERIMENTS

Fabrication

Poly(L-lactic acid) was dissolved in TFE at room temperature with a homogenous

solution. The PLLA concentration was 8wt% by volume.

An experimental setup for fabricating aligned nanofibers is shown schematically in **Fig 1**, of which the tip-to-collector distance was set to 10 ± 2 cm and the collecting time was 4min. The electrospinning was done at an ambient temperature (25°C) with a humidity of 40-60%. The flow rate was adjusted to 3ml h^{-1} and the electrical voltage was 25kV.

The fiber bundles taken off rotating disc were transferred to a custom-made device, which was a combination of hot-stretching and twisting. A tension ratio of about 50% with a heating temperature of 80°C was applied, and the tensile force was kept for 2 hours. The post treated fiber bundles were made into a braided wire through a minitype braiding machine.

For surface coating, chitosan was chosen as the coating material. The chitosan solution was prepared by dissolving it in a suitable amount of acetic acid to obtain a weight ratio of 1%. Then the PLLA nanofiber wires were dripped into the chitosan solution and stirred for 30min. After that, the chitosan coated PLLA wires (called PLLA-CS sutures) were washed three times with 0.1M NaOH solution and with deionized water.

Characterization

Morphology of the collected fibers was observed under an environmental scanning electron microscopy (ESEM, PHILIPS XL 30, Netherlands). The fibrous bundles and braided wires were examined under an optical microscope (Union D23, Olympus, Japan). The diameters of the electrospun fibers were measured through image visualization software ImageJ 1.34s.

Tensile properties were measured according to ASTM Standard D 2256-02 [22]. Hemolytic properties of the PLLA and PLLA-CS sutures were examined by spectrophotometry[23]. Kinetic hemostasis experiment was also carried out. To understand platelet and erythrocyte adhesion behavior on the PLLA and PLLA-CS sutures, opposite experiment was done[23]. Estimation of sutures' cytotoxicity, cell morphology and proliferation was performed by direct contact of human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) with a leaching liquor of the PLLA and PLLA-CS sutures[24]. Animal experiment was prepared to study muscle histopathology after sutures implanted[24].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Surface topography analysis

A grounded rotating disk with a sharp edge was used to collect aligned electrospun fibers. A fiber bundle thread was obtained after 4min collection. Our previous work [25] has demonstrated an optimal rotation rate of about 1205 RPM, which was used in this study. **Fig. 3a** is SEM micrograph of the aligned fibers, taken from the rim of the disk. It can be seen that the fibers made from PLLA solution with 8 wt% concentration had good topography, without any beads on the fiber surface. An averaged fiber diameter was 667nm. The collecting time was chosen as 4 min after duplicate experiment. A SEM image (**Fig. 3b**, denoted by an arrow) confirmed that deposition of chitosan on the PLLA suture surface was achieved.

Tensile property

Tensile stress-strain curves of the PLLA and PLLA-CS sutures without and with a "O" knot were shown in **Fig. 4**. It can be seen that the curves essentially exhibited a bilinear behavior with an initial elastic segment followed by a plastic one. The tensile property parameters are listed in **Table 1**. The diameter of the braided sutures was of

about $0.35\text{mm}\pm 0.05\text{mm}$ (**Fig. 5**). All of the braided suture samples showed a breaking force of around 8.8 N, which is close to 10.2 N required by a 2-0 type collagen suture with a diameter from 0.35mm to 0.399mm specified in the American Pharmacopoeia Standard [26]. As for the knot strength, both samples presented similar mechanical properties, and the knot strength was slightly lower than the tensile strength, which was about 84MPa. It can be found that the present braided sutures are applicable in terms of the tensile strength and the knot strength, which are the most important properties for a suture in clinic applications.

Hemolytic property

Blood compatibility of the sutures was estimated by their hemolytic ratio (HR). A material with excellent blood compatibility should have a low hemolysis ratio [27], which is lower than 5% [28]. The measured blood compatibility data are summarized in **Table 2**. It can be seen that both the PLLA and the PLLA-CS sutures had HR values lower than 5%, indicating that both the sutures exhibited good blood compatibility [29].

Kinetic Hemostasis

Hemolysis occurs when red blood cells within uncoagulated blood come into contact with water. So, the absorbency of the water reflects the uncoagulated quantity of the blood on contact with the suture. A higher absorbency indicated that the solution contained more concentrated hemoglobin, namely, the less blood was coagulated on the surface of the suture. The quicker the absorbency decreased with the time, the shorter the clotting time was, and the better hemostatic effect the materials had.

Figure 6 shows the dynamic blood clotting profiles for two kinds of sutures. The absorbency of the hemolyzed hemoglobin solution decreased with an increased contact time of blood with the samples. In addition, the absorbency of the solution for PLLA-CS suture was decreasing more quickly than that for the PLLA suture without chitosan, and approximately near to that for glass sample at 10 min on which the blood coagulation generally occurred after 5 min contact. This showed that the chitosan coated on PLLA suture could induce the blood coagulation and had a good hemostatic property.

Platelet adhesion

In normal hemostasis, platelets play a crucial role. Plasma protein is absorbed firstly on the surface of materials when blood contacts with the materials, followed by adherence and deformation of the platelets and then startup a cruor process. The platelet adhesion on each sample was qualitatively assessed based on the morphology of SEM images. **Figures 7a** and **7b** illustrate the platelets which have contacted with surfaces of the PLLA and PLLA-CS sutures for 30 min, respectively. It was observed that the platelets adhered strongly on the surfaces of both the sutures. Furthermore, the platelets were bound to each other and formed an aggregated mass. The platelets on the PLLA-CS sutures were greater in number than those on the PLLA sutures, but most of the adhered platelets were round with only a few filopodia.

Erythrocyte Adhesion

Aggregation of erythrocytes also plays an important role in hemostasis. The adhesion of erythrocyte on each sample was shown in **Fig.8**. The erythrocytes adhered strongly on surfaces of both the PLLA and PLLA-CS sutures and formed an aggregation mass. Obviously, the sutures coated with chitosan absorbed more erythrocytes than the ones without chitosan coating. In addition, the erythrocytes on the surface of the plain PLLA sample exhibited a smooth morphology (**Fig. 8a**), whereas those on the surface of the PLLA-CS sample (**Fig. 8b**) were seen to possess pseudopodias and were bound to each other in an aggregating form. This indicated that the PLLA-CS attracted and

activated the erythrocytes effectively. It can be informed that the PLLA-CS suture showed better hemagglutination than the PLLA suture because of a dual function of platelets and erythrocytes together with the introduction of chitosan. This could also be used to explain the results in a kinetic hemostasis experiment.

MTT assay

Cellular viability was quantitatively assessed by using MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-5-(3-carboxymethoxyphenyl)-2-(4-sulfophenyl)-2H-tetrazolium) assay, which could reflect any damage of material's toxicity on cells with high sensitivity. The effect of the material's leaching liquor on cell growth was designated through coloration by means of the MTT assay, and the cell growth and proliferation could be determined by examining material absorption by an indirect contact[22]. In order to show cellular toxicity, the leaching liquors of the sample with different concentrations, i.e., 100%, 75%, 50%, and 25%, and cultured for different time periods, i.e., 1d, 3d, 5d, and 7d, were used in this study. It has been found that the PLLA-CS suture exhibited essentially no negative effect on the cell proliferation. **Table 3** summarized the measured RGR data of the samples which were all greater than 85%, indicating that the cellular toxicity was less than or at most equal to the 1st level. In other words, the PLLA-CS suture exhibited essentially no cellular toxicity.

Cell morphology and proliferation

Fig. 9 shows a proliferation process of the human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) after being cultured for 7 days. The cell morphology and growth was observed and photographed by an inverted microscope once every two days. It can be seen from **Fig. 9a** that partial of the cells were anchorage-dependent with a circular shape after cultured with the leaching liquor for 1 day. Three days later, few circular cells could be seen and the HUVECs were in vigorous growth and anchorage-dependent favorably. The cell shapes became fusiform and irregularly polygonal. On the 5th day, the cell number enlarged pronouncedly with an increased cell diameter, and the geometric shapes of the cells were mainly fusiform and irregularly polygonal. On the 7th day, the shapes were not changed, but the cells grew more vigorously and located densely. However, in the masculine control group indicated in **Fig. 9i** there were scarcely viable cells, which had become circular. Lots of the dead cells could be seen under the microscope.

Animal model

In order to further understand whether the developed braided PLLA nanofiber wire could be sutured inside a body, an animal test was done in this work. Photos of the PLLA-CS braided wire sutured inside forelimb muscle of a SD mouse imbedded after the 1st day and the 28th day are shown in **Fig. 10** respectively. The photos clearly demonstrated that the PLLA-CS braided wire displayed a preferable suturing effect with a sound knot and the wound was healing up smoothly. The musculature behaviors in the presence of the PLLA-CS suture and a commercial silk suture were evaluated at different periods of time (3-28 days). After the implantation for three days, both the PLLA-CS suture and the silk suture were soaked with a large number of inflammatory cells as shown in **Fig. 11**, which were mainly centrioles and concentrated around the sutures. Granulation tissues were irregularly distributed and observed in an incipient way on the 3rd day. Suture segments could be seen clearly in **Figs. 11(b) and 11(e)** respectively, as marked with arrows. There were still lots of inflammatory cells around the anastomotic wound on the 7th day after the implantation. The PLLA-CS suture group was found less inflammation than the silk suture group. Fibrous tissue hyperplasia could be observed on the 14th day with the PLLA-CS suture group, which were mainly macrophages, and a few neutrophils and

lymphocytes occurred. The silk suture group still had relatively plenty of inflammatory cells even after the implantation for 14 days.

CONCLUSIONS

Chitosan coated PLLA braided wires were successfully fabricated by using electrospinning technique followed by braiding. This new type of sutures exhibited preferable blood compatibility, hemostatic behavior and histocompatibility, have no effect on cellular morphology and proliferation, which is consistent with the standard of medical material. Tensile and knot strengths of the developed sutures were also acceptable.

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Fig. 1 Experimental setup for preparing aligned electrospun fibers used in this study

Fig.3 SEM photographs of a) aligned electrospun fibers and b) chitosan coated PLLA suture (chitosan that has been deposited on nanofibers as indicated by the arrow)

Fig. 4 Tensile stress-strain curves of PLLA and PLLA-CS sutures and their knot strength

Fig. 5 Optical microscope photograph of braided wire

Fig.6 Dynamic hemostasis process for PLLA suture (I), PLLA-CS suture (II) and a reference glass (III).

Fig. 7 SEM images of adherent platelets ($\times 1000$) on (a) PLLA suture and (b) PLLA-CS suture

Fig. 8 Morphology of human erythrocytes ($\times 5000$) for blood mixed with (a) PLLA suture, (b) PLLA-CS suture

Fig. 9 Distributions of Human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) and their morphology: (a)-(d) were done using the leaching liquors cultured with the PLLA-CS sutures for different times (1, 3, 5, 7 days) respectively, and (e) corresponded to the masculine control group

Fig. 10 Photos of rats' forelimb implanted with different sutures (indicated with arrows): (a) and (b) represented the PLLA-CS sutures sutured for 1 day and 28 days, respectively.

Fig.8 Histology sections of PLLA-CS suture and silk suture stained with hematoxylin and eosin: (a)-(c) were PLLA-CS sutures implanted after 3, 14 and 28 days, (d)-(f)

were silk sutures imbeded after 3, 14 and 28 days respectively, and (g) corresponded to the common muscle control group

Table 1 Tensile property

Sample	Diameter / mm	Breaking Force / N	Breaking Strength / MPa	Breaking Strain / %	Youngs Modules / MPa
PLLA	0.35±0.02	8.78±1.95	91.27±10.38	78.48±8.72	586.88±101.32
PLLA-CS	0.35±0.03	8.65±1.83	89.99±8.67	78.12±6.78	443.68±94.53
PLLA _{knotted}	0.35±0.02	8.09±1.85	84.19±7.37	76.21±6.78	416.74±89.63
PLLA-CS _{knotted}	0.35±0.03	7.99±1.36	83.15±6.56	79.94±5.36	382.64±58.35

Table 2 The hemolysis experimental results

Sample	X ±s (A _{545nm})	HR
A _P	0.764	4.75% (PLLA)
A _N	0.006	
A _{S/PLLA}	0.042	
A _{S/PLLA-CS}	0.037	4.08% (PLLA-CS)

Table 3 Material toxicity data (RGR/ toxicity level)

Group	Concentration of Leaching liquor/ %	RGR / %				Toxicity Level			
		1d	3d	5d	7d	1d	3d	5d	7d
PLLA-CS Suture Group	100	99.8±2.3	97.7±2.5	94.3±5.9	88.3±2.6	1	1	1	1
	75	100.6±3.4	86.6±3.6	94.2±2.5	99.7±5.2	0	1	1	1
	50	104.2±4.0	94.2±3.7	92.4±4.6	90.7±2.8	0	1	1	1
	25	102.7±2.2	101.7±4.0	106.0±4.8	109.2±4.8	0	0	0	0
Negative control group	100	100	100	100	0	0	0	0	
Masculine control group		11.37±1.3	4.6±1.1	2.8±0.5	0.0±0.0	4	4	4	5